

Towards Personalized Social Recommendations

Methods and technology to enable cohesive and inclusive recommendations

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The aim of the SPICE project is to build social cohesion, both between and within citizen communities, by developing tools and methods to support *citizen curation*. We define *citizen curation* as a process in which cultural objects are used as a resource by citizens to develop their own personal interpretations. Within communities, citizens can use their interpretations to build a representation of themselves and their shared perspective on culture. Interpretations can also be used to support social cohesion across groups. In this short position paper we outline the methodologies and technologies needed to be built in order to build a recommender system of cultural objects that will implement these goals of social cohesion and inclusion.

CCS CONCEPTS • Information systems~Information retrieval~Retrieval tasks and goals~Clustering and classification • Information systems~Information retrieval~Retrieval tasks and goals~Recommender systems • Information systems~Information retrieval~Retrieval tasks and goals~Sentiment analysis

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Semantic Text analysis, User Model, Community model, Social Recommender

ACM Reference Format:

Belen Diaz Agudo, Alessio Bosca, Andrea Bolioli, Guillermo Jimenez Diaz, Tsvi Kuflik, Alan J. Wecker. 2021. Towards Personalized Social Recommendations. Methods and technology to enable cohesive and inclusive recommendations. PATCH 2021, co-located with UMAP 2021, June 21-25, Utrecht, the Netherlands, 4 pages.

1 INTRODUCTION

Normally, recommender systems in general and recommender systems for cultural heritage in particular, try to maximize the satisfaction of each individual choice by the user. This can be motivated by the goal of, not necessarily of the end user, but by organizations trying to promote a certain item. In recent years a broader view of recommendation goals has been established such as *diversity*, and *serendipity* (Kotkov et al., 2020). In this paper, we describe technologies to advance

additional goals of applying novel recommendation techniques for promoting *social cohesion* and *inclusion* s part of our work on an EU Horizon 2020 project SPICE¹. Our approach includes the community feeling (Adler, 1964) as a useful component of the recommender algorithm that takes into account not only the individual preferences but also the individuals' awareness of being part of a certain community and how this feeling affects individuals' preferences when dealing with a set of communities in the social world. Community feeling is beneficial both for the individual and for society. Our approach also includes use of techniques of Citizen Curation (Ellwood et al., 2018; Neill, 2017; Robinson & Carletti, 2019). In the SPICE project we define Citizen Curation (Bruni et al., 2020) as *citizens applying curatorial methods to archival materials available in heritage and memory institutions as well as to items depicted in exhibitions in order to develop their own interpretations, share their own perspective and appreciate the perspectives of others*. While our approach will clearly be to the benefit of society, we believe that this also reflects the values of the individual user who wishes to better understand their context and environment. The goal here is that each member of society feel that he has a part in the cultural heritage in some manner and while not to come to a common understanding/interpretation but that each individual will understand and perhaps even empathize towards other members of his society's divergent views. In this short position paper we outline the methodologies and technologies needed to be built in order to build a recommender system that will implement these goals. To illustrate our ultimate goal we describe the following scenario:

Lara decides to view a Citizen Curation activity at a museum she is visiting. The activity involves selecting an artwork from the museum's collection, listening to an interpretation. Afterwards, Lara is notified of an interpretation of the artwork contributed by someone from a different social group from the one she heard earlier. The interpretation is a personal story prompted by the artwork recorded as audio. The story is accompanied by comments responding positively to the story contributed by people in the first social group. Lara decides to listen to it. Before the audio recording starts, Lara is encouraged to imagine how the storyteller feels about what happened. The story is very different from the first interpretation of the artwork. She adds her own comment after listening.

2 METHODOLOGY

We describe three technologies that are critical bases for a Social Recommender System: Semantic Text Analysis, User Modelling, Community Modelling. Each tool builds on its predecessor to accomplish its goals; thus the text analysis tool provides information from user generated content which can be used to populate the user model. The user model and info from the text analysis tool is used to provide input for the community model. The user and community models are part of the input for the social recommender.

2.1 Analyzing User Contents: Semantic Annotator

The semantic annotator is a component for the semantic enrichment of textual contents (linking content to concepts described in a knowledge graph), targeting user generated contents as well as descriptions of museum artifacts. Semantically tagged documents are easier to find, interpret, combine and reuse.

The annotator provides identifiers of concepts and entities mentioned in the text or relevant to it. These references link the textual contents to the formal descriptions of these concepts/entities in a knowledge graph and enables further reasoning over them.

The Semantic Annotator performs Sentiment Analysis (Daiber et al., 2013), Emotion Detection (Barbieri et al., 2018; Sprugnoli, 2020) and Entity Linking; it is multilingual and supports all the languages used in museum use cases: English, Finnish, Hebrew, Italian and Spanish. The process of semantic annotation is realized by a Natural Language Pipeline that includes different analysis modules (each one responsible for annotating the document with respect to a specific aspect: sentiment analysis, emotion detection, entity linking); the overall process is exposed by means of standard RESTful APIS and produces a JSON-LD document as output. JSON-LD is a json based serialization for linked data that can be seamlessly stored in the SPICE linked data hub.

¹ SPICE: "Social cohesion, Participation, and Inclusion through Cultural Engagement" <https://spice-h2020.eu/>. It is an EU project aiming to foster diverse participation in the heritage domain through a process of "citizen curation".

The analysis module included in the pipeline are:

- Language Analysis, for performing standard language analysis on the contents (e.g. lemmatization, pos tagging) that is exploited by the Emotion Detection and Sentiment Analysis components.
- Emotion Detection, for detecting textual expressions that can be linked to emotions.
- Sentiment Analysis, for detecting textual expressions that carry a subjective information (e.g. like and dislike statements) along with its polarity: positive, negative or neutral. The conceptual framework used to model sentiment polarity is the Marl ontology, a standardized data schema designed to annotate and describe subjective opinions expressed on the web or in particular Information Systems.
- Entity Linking, for detecting textual expressions that can be linked to relevant concepts and named entities in order to obtain a representation of the semantics of the contents through the detected entities and their types. Since the topics of user generated contents (as well as the subjects of museums use cases) cannot be restricted to a specific domain we decided to use DBPedia as the target conceptual framework.

In the context of SPICE project reasoning over such semantic annotation allows for abstracting and generalizing input coming from museum visitors, finding commonalities between them and ultimately supporting the activity of users and communities modelling and the design of an advanced recommender system.

2.2 User Modeling

User models (Cena et al., 2019; Kuflik et al., 2014; Mokatren et al., 2019; Musto et al., 2018) represent the individuals that are interacting with the system. They are key elements (together with the community models) used to guide the process of content recommendations to individuals, taking into consideration individual and group interests, to search and identify relevant users' contributions, to provide alternative interpretations of objects, to promote the social contagion among users and to emphasize the similarities and differences intra and inter communities.

There are a number of basic concepts we consider:

User This is an individual who we model based on **properties** that are organized into different **categories**. A property is configured by giving it a name, how it is constrained (what are allowable values) and aggregations strategy (how do we handle multiple calls to configure this property). Aggregation strategies can be latest (last one given), average (mean of all values given) or weighted average (mean with later entries given more weight). In addition, when a property is added one can add information such as in what **context** the information was added and what was the **source** of the information and whether it was **explicitly** given by the user or **implicitly** derived based on some observed behaviour or other factors.

Here is an elucidation of the categories which we wish to model: **Identity** – These are properties which identify the user (I.e. ID, email, password) , **Demographics** – Descriptives of the user which are fairly stable (age, gender, place of birth), **Traits** – Values which describe the user (e.g. personality, learning style ...) , **Beliefs/Values** - Items the user holds (thinks are important) to be of value, **Interests**- Items that the user likes. Could be evidenced by how long he views an artifact connected to an interest, **Skills** – Things that the user is good at or believes they are good at, **Communities**- Either explicit communities obtained from user info or explicitly derived communities from community model, **Current Contexts** – Info about the user's current environment. For communities we want to bootstrap off demographics to form explicit communities and then use interests and values to construct implicit communities.

The reasoning mechanism of the user modeling component in SPICE is based on a possible combination of explicit and implicit user modeling. - Users may be able to bootstrap their user model before or at the beginning of a visit by providing information about who they are and what they like explicitly. During their visit, visitors' behavior, including time spent and interaction with exhibits and the results of the textual analysis of content they provide may be used to continuously update the model.

2.3 Community Modelling

Communities are key elements (together with the user models) to search and browse contents of interests, to identify similarities and differences across users and their contributions, to provide alternative interpretations of objects, to promote the social contagion among users and to emphasize the similarities and differences intra and inter communities. Communities are groups of users with shared characteristics. Community detection algorithms use features

from the user model, like similar personal profile features (demographics, age, sex,..) and also features regarding the user opinions and emotions on items of the content model. The set of communities represents the context of a certain user and they support the exploration of interpretations and museum objects and help the recommender to find contents of interest. The visualization and explanation of communities allow the exploration, reflective reasoning and social cohesion of the users. Besides, communities of users that have previously used the system enable overcoming the cold start problem as, due to similarity intra-community, a new user can be treated like other users from the same community. A user may belong to many different communities as they provide different contexts and common features with other users. Besides, the set of communities is variable through time as new users and opinions may arise in the system. Communities can be explicitly stated (according to the information provided by the user model) or implicit, i.e., computed by the community detection algorithms using similarity metrics. Explicit communities represent user archetypes summarizing common behaviors (like teachers/children if we are in a children school visit to a museum). Communities can also be classified as persistent, which are those that are stable in time and can be defined as part of the user model; or virtual communities, which have a temporary and dynamic character and arise with new users, new opinions, stories and/or reflections. They are detected using the community detection algorithms and can become persistent if required.

There are different community detection algorithms based on clustering (Xu & Tian, 2015) and on graph analysis (Fortunato, 2010; Yang et al., 2016). What is relevant for this task is that community detection algorithms will heavily rely on the definition of semantic similarity metrics. For example, we may be interested in communities of users that share similar personal profile features from the user model and could also combine these by identifying similar interpretations on similar contents. The use of different similarity metrics will change the set of communities in the community model and this is why we need to include configuration capabilities using a catalog of semantic similarity metrics. Another interesting aspect that is very relevant for the recommender system is the capability of explanation of the community model. That means that each community should be explained to understand, for example, why a certain user belongs to a certain community, what are the commonalities shared by the users of this community and what are the differences within other nearby communities. A community can be explained through the similarity metric used to detect it, or by means of the common set of relations between its users. A symbolic description can be also built using graph-based analysis techniques (like Formal Concept Analysis) (Jorro et al., 2020).

3 EVALUATION

The system can evaluate attitudes by questionnaires before and after visiting an exhibition concerning their empathy to other peoples' views. Additionally, we can do behavioral measurements such as the level of activity and engagement with diverse content throughout an activity, by comparison with "traditional" visit to the exhibition. In a broader view, we need to evaluate user experience and satisfaction with recommendations that provide for social cohesion and satisfaction. In a narrower more specific sense, there is a need to measure how effective our tools were in promoting such goals (did we really measure the empathy in the user generated content, does the user model really reflect the user's values and interests, did we discover real implicit communities).

4 DISCUSSION

One of the goals of developing the above technologies will be to use them in a recommender system which can provide recommendations based on similar/dissimilar groups both implicit/explicit. In this position paper, we advanced the position that such tools are feasible and have shown a roadmap to their implementation.

While most of this position paper has discussed the technical aspects of providing the technological basis for tools to improve inclusion and social cohesion, perhaps here is the time to discuss the need for such tools. While inclusion is an obvious goal, in that, every cultural heritage institution wants to increase its audience base; social cohesion as a goal for museums is more complex. In a previous paper (Wecker & Kuflik, 2015) we described the need and requirements to increase diversity; social cohesion goes beyond that. Our previous paper argued for the need and choice in viewing diversity, here we advance the position, while still agreeing with our opinion on the rights of individuals to choose in matters of diversity, we need to provide tools and technology which help broker the diversity to individual users as a worthy technological goal that should be pursued.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant agreement n° 870811).

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